

Entropy as a Measure of the Response to Stochastic Interactions

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Shannon's entropy, one form of entropy, is expressed in terms of probabilities, i.e. $S = - \sum \text{over } i P(i) \ln(P(i))$, where $P(i)$ is the probability for event i . One may use probabilities for different events and hence obtain different entropies. Thermodynamic entropy is associated with the first law of thermodynamics $dE = TdS - PdV$. As a result, this entropy is linked to energy changes. Energy changes occur due to interactions, so we suggest that thermodynamic entropy is linked to the stochastic response of a system to interactions. These may be either internal interactions, as in the case of a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas or quantum bound state, or external as in the gas of a photon bath exciting a particle to various different quantum bound states or heat/work being associated with an MB gas. Thus, as argued in (1) one may create Shannon entropy expressions using probabilities for events which are not created by a stochastic potential. In such a case, the entropy is an informational one, but not a thermodynamic one.

We point out, however, that there may be different energies in a system. For example, a quantum bound state contains a superposition of free particle states $\exp(ipx)$ which are associated with the energy $pp/2m$ which may be measured if one knocks out a bound particle. The stochastic interactions of $V(x)$ give rise to E_n which is associated with a dE of $E_{n+1} - E_n$. On the other hand, one may have a stochastic absorption/emission of photons and dE is then dE_{average} . In other words, one may have different energies and thermodynamic entropies, but a higher level energy is influenced by lower level stochastic interactions as will be explained in the note.

Classical mechanics is said to be deterministic, but we argue that in statistical mechanics the measure of an average is an attempt to create a deterministic value. Instead of considering different values with probabilities, one assigns one average value to simplify and remove the notion of probability. It is thus possible that classical mechanics, a deterministic theory, is one of averages. If such a deterministic average theory suffices, as it does in many cases, why deal with probabilities? Experimentally a free quantum particle exhibits interference/diffraction associated with probability in space for a fixed momentum. This is an example of behaviour which is not described by an average deterministic classical mechanical theory. As a result, there seems to be a built-in stochasticity even for a deterministic constant momentum, perhaps due to a set of internal stochastic interactions. This is at odds with the classical mechanical notion of a fixed potential energy at a given x , even though kinetic energy is $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistically) for a free particle. Given the inherent spatial probability, it seems that interactions which take place in space, e.g. $V(x)$, must also be associated with this stochasticity, but at the same time represents a second set of stochastic interactions. Finally, one may have stochastic absorption/emission of photons leading to a third set of stochastic interactions, influenced by the previous two.

We consider these ideas in this note.

Informational Versus Thermodynamic Entropy

Shannon's entropy is given by: $S = - \sum \text{over } i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ ((1)), where $P(i)$ is the probability for an event. For example, one may toss a coin and use $P(\text{heads})=.5$ and $P(\text{tails})=.5$. We call this informational entropy because it is associated with a lack of information about the result of the toss. In other words, it captures possible results using probabilities.

In thermodynamics, there is a thermodynamic entropy which appears in the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \text{ where } P \text{ is pressure, } V \text{ volume and } S \text{ entropy} \quad ((2))$$

S is probabilistic if one uses ((1)), but must, at the same time, be linked with energy. Energy is

associated with interactions (e.g. impulse hits, work etc), We suggest that thermodynamic entropy is linked with stochastic response of a system to stochastic interactions. In a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, these stochastic interactions are two body elastic collisions. (1) uses the term subjective entropy and presents the following example. Imagine a room with a battery powered heater. The heater may be on or off. This is an informational situation, like the tossing of the coin. One may create a subjective or information entropy based on the probabilities for the heater to be on or off, but this has nothing to do with a physical state. If the battery is on, (1) argues, there is an internal thermodynamic entropy associated with interactions caused by the heater. If it is off, there is a different thermodynamic entropy associated with whatever interactions exist with the battery off. There are no interactions involved with switching the battery on and off and back on ect in a stochastic manner and so (1) argues that trying to create an ensemble including states with the battery on and with the battery off is a subjective entropy and not a thermodynamic one. We suggest that thermodynamic entropy is associated with the response of a system to stochastic interactions. In other words, thermodynamics is closely linked with the physics of interactions in a system and is not simply informational entropy

This immediately raises a question: What if there are multiple stochastic interactions in a system?

Multiple Stochastic Interactions In a System

It is possible for a system to have multiple stochastic interactions. We argued that thermodynamic entropy measures the response of a system to stochastic interactions and is associated with energy. If there are multiple types of stochastic interactions, there may be multiple types of energy. Thus, thermodynamic entropy may be calculated for a specific stochastic interaction in the system or one might try to calculate an overall thermodynamic entropy for combined stochastic interactions. The first law of thermodynamics, however, contains the term dE which represents a change in energy. One may then ask: What stochastic interactions change the energy? In such a case, there may be only one kind of interaction and hence one thermodynamic entropy, even though there exists stochasticity associated with another type of interaction. One must be careful because there may be different kinds of energy or even average energy which is changed.

As an example, consider a quantum bound state. There exist stochastic hits from a potential $V(x)$ which lead to a resonance of free particle probability states i.e.

$$\text{Wavefunction} = W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

These states $\exp(ipx)$ themselves represent a response to stochastic internal interactions, we argue and so in principle one could calculate a free particle entropy using $C \cos(px)$ as a probability over a half cycle where it is positive.

Overall, there is a bound state energy E_n , for a level n . One may create a Shannon's entropy using a probability of $W(x)W(x)$ for space and one for momentum using $a(p)a(p)$, as is often done in the literature, or add the two as we have suggested previously. Such an entropy measures a response to stochastic interactions with $V(x)$, but has a fixed energy E_n , as in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. One may systematically try to change energy, i.e. dE , but this means moving from E_n to E_{n+1} . This is a different thermodynamic entropy, although influenced by $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. by the lower level of stochastic interactions.

One may have a system, however, with a single particle which may occupy a set of E_n values. A stochastic source of photons may be available which knocks the particle into different E_n states, which then decay by emitting a photon. Here the stochastic interaction is not $V(x)$, but the photon as E_n states have constant values. dE in such a case is associated with the stochastic photon interactions, i.e. with changes in E_{average} not E_n to E_{n+1} , and one may calculate a different thermodynamic entropy using:

$$P(E_n) = C \exp(-E_n/T) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, thermodynamic entropy seems to be associated with a particular type of stochastic interaction which is linked to the possible change in a specific kind of energy in the system.

Deterministic Theories

Classical mechanics is a deterministic theory. One may at first argue that deterministic theories are the opposite of statistical ones, but we argue that the statistical notion of an average is an attempt to create a deterministic value. Instead of considering multiple possibilities with probabilities, one considers one known, deterministic average value and hence incorporates the stochasticity into the average value which is then treated in a deterministic manner. For example, temperature T in thermodynamics is treated in such a manner, or pressure as well. One may then consider how these values change in time without worrying about the microscopic details. This is well-known in the literature, but one usually does not associate classical motion with such an argument. It is usually presented as a deterministic theory for which there is no probability.

The problem with this, we argue, is the n -slit interference/diffraction experimental results. These cannot be described by deterministic classical mechanics, but require a probabilistic description of a freely moving particle. A free quantum particle has a fixed momentum and kinetic energy at each x point, but there is a kind of a probability in x given by its wavefunction:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is a periodic eigenfunction of the translation operator d/dx (i.e. $-id/dx$). In other words, probability in space is linked with translational invariance for a free particle. This does not seem to be stochastic response to a stochastic interaction, unless one argues that ((4)) is the result of the interaction which created the momentum p in the first place, i.e. the impulse hit. In other words, an impulse hit may change p to p_1 , but there are spatial probabilistic consequences. In such a case, one should not think of a momentum hit as simply occurring at a point x , it has probabilistic consequences over the range of a wavelength.

If this is the case, then one needs to reexamine the deterministic classical mechanical equation:

$$\text{Kinetic energy}(x) + \text{Potential energy}(x) = E \text{ constant} \quad ((5))$$

This suggests that a kinetic energy exists at point x , while $\exp(ipx)$ suggests that it exists at least over a range of a wavelength \hbar/p . To resolve this discrepancy, one may suggest that ((5)) represents average values. The interaction with $V(x)$ also does not take place at a point, but over a wavelength. Thus $V(x)$ is in a sense an average value as well. As a result, ((5)) is a constraint equation for average values (energy in this case) which governs a stochastic process. In other words, $V(x)$ delivers stochastic interactions and the system responds in dynamic manner, instead of the stochastic one of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas which absorbs heat without the volume changing.

How does one model the probability for the stochastic hits from the potential $V(x)$? For example,

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k P(k,x), \text{ but } P(k,x) \text{ is unknown} \quad ((6))$$

The average equation ((5)) shows that one does not need to know the form of $P(k,x)$. It is enough to know the form of kinetic energy which is computed using $\exp(ipx)$, which follows from translational invariance, i.e.

$$KE(x) = \left(\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right) / \left(\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx) \right) \quad ((7))$$

or $KE(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W / W \quad ((8))$

As a result, a deterministic average equation may be used to calculate $a(p)$ values which measure the response of a free particle to stochastic interactions from $V(x)$ subject to the constraint that a free particle contains a stochasticity described by $\exp(ipx)$ and conservation of energy. We argued that $\exp(ipx)$ may be a manifestation of internal type stochastic interactions and so the bound state system contains two sets of stochastic interactions, the ones creating $\exp(ipx)$ and $V(x)$. When one calculates Shannon's momentum entropy using $a(p)a(p)$ as the probability, this measures the response to $V(x)$, but the values of $a(p)$ are influenced by the form $\exp(ipx)$. Using $W(x)W(x)$ as the probability, on the other hand combines explicitly the effects of internal stochastic interactions and $V(x)$. The internal stochastic interactions are associated with changes in p values, but one is usually concerned with the bound state energy E_n . Thus, there are different energies involved, namely the stochastic $pp/2m$ values and E_n . Experimentally, one may measure $a(p)$ by knocking out a bound state particle from many systems. One may measure E_n , by absorbing light or measuring emitted light. Thus interaction used to measure energy differs and this points to different notions of thermodynamic entropy as well.

The above example may be taken a step further by suggesting that photons be absorbed or emitted stochastically. In such a case, E_n is no longer the energy of interest, but average is. Probability values, however, are $\exp(-E_n/T)$, so E_n values influence the result, just $\exp(ipx)$ values influence the form of average kinetic energy.

As a result, there may be different kinds of stochastic interactions in a problem, different energies of concern and different kinds of thermodynamic entropies. One may focus on a particular stochastic interaction and its associated energy changes, but the other interactions influence this thermodynamic entropy value.

Conclusion

Entropy is often presented as Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ where $P(i)$ is the probability for event i . This is an informational entropy, i.e. one which may be applied to the tossing of a coin or die. Thermodynamic entropy is associated with the first law of thermodynamics $dE = TdS - PdV$, which in turn is linked with changes in energy. These may occur due to stochastic processes, so a thermodynamic entropy is associated with special probabilities which measure the response to stochastic interactions.

In this note, we suggest, however, that there may be a set of stochastic interactions present in a problem, associated with different energies. In a problem, however, one focuses on a specific dE and this leads to a specific $P(i)$ and a specific Shannon's entropy, which is thermodynamic entropy associated with the particular dE . $P(i)$ is nevertheless influenced, we argue, by the other stochastic interactions present. As an example, we consider a free quantum particle. It has constant p and $pp/2m$, but a spatial kind of probability $\exp(ipx)$. We suggest that this is associated with internal type forces and linked with the momentum hit which created p in the first place. This is the first set of stochastic interactions and one may calculate an entropy for a free particle using a probability of $\cos(px)$ over half a cycle (positive values). Given the form of $\exp(ipx)$, which is experimentally verifiable through n -slit experiments, one cannot have a change in p occur at a point. It is associated with a wavelength. Classical conservation of energy seems to be an equation of averages which give the appearance of a deterministic theory. One may use $\exp(ipx)$ to calculate the form of $KE(x)$ average and use conservation of energy to solve for $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, i.e. the response to the second stochastic interaction set $\exp(ipx)$. One obtains $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ which may be used to obtain probabilities $W(x)W(x)$ and $a(p)a(p)$ which are used in the literature to calculate Shannon's entropies. These entropies, however, are influenced by the form $\exp(ipx)$ which gives rise to the $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ kinetic energy term. In such a case, dE (change in energy) is associated with changing from E_n to E_{n+1} .

One may go one step further and consider a third set of stochastic interactions, i.e. the absorption and emission of photons. In such a case, E_n is not the focus, but E_{average} . dE means now dE_{average} and P is $C \exp(-E_n/T)$. E_n , however, is influenced by the stochastic interactions of $V(x)$, but also by the form $\exp(ipx)$ which is caused by the internal interactions associated with free motion.

References

1. Goldstein, S. And Lebowitz, J. And Tumulka, K. And Zanghi N. Gibbs and Boltzmann Entropy in Classical and Quantum Mechanics. 2019
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